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THE IMPACT OF WOMEN OF CENTRAL ASIA IN DIPLOMACY

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Annotation: *This project presents a study of “female presence” in diplomacy of five Central Asian countries: Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and Uzbekistan in the period of independence. It investigates the origins and consequences of women’s role and impact, as well as issues of gender asymmetry in the politics and diplomacy. Women are still underrepresented in diplomacy, particularly in senior positions. The project analyze problems and prospects for the advancement of women -carrier diplomats, and expansion of their women participation in the political and diplomatic institutions, research institutes/centers, policy groups, and panels of experts. The project is directed to help address this issue, understand what obstacles remain and how they can be overcome. The project aims to share knowledge and tools about how to create better access to and accelerate women’s representation in the national and international political and diplomatic organisations. It also examines how to more effectively integrate a gender-lens into government action and policy-making. The paper examines the historical background, social and professional environment, institutional barriers facing women diplomats, as well as current trends in women's participation in shaping the policy of the region's states. The project is based on a comparative analysis of the legal framework, national and international statistics, including UN reports, academic research, interviews, and public speeches. There is also an overview of women's representation in diplomatical and political activity based on the Women in Diplomacy indicators, which reflects the proportion of women diplomats, senior executive officers. Particular attention is paid to the practical aspects of women's participation in policy and diplomacy: career mobility, representation at the international and regional levels, as well as state policies to advance women in diplomacy. The study identifies both positive trends in gender empowering and persistent challenges related to cultural stereotypes, limited institutional support, and social barriers. The study offers recommendations for strengthening women's role in diplomacy through legislative reform, training, and strengthening regional and international cooperation.*

Keywords: *gender equality, career diplomats, female diplomats, women empowering.*

Introduction

The role of women in diplomacy and politics has become an increasingly important topic in the context of globalization and the broader pursuit of sustainable development. Progress for women in diplomacy has been much slower and more uneven than progress toward formal gender equality. Gender equality remains one of the defining challenges of our time, as reflected in Sustainable Development Goal 5, which calls for achieving gender equality and empowering all women and girls by 2030. Women are still underrepresented in diplomacy and remain far from achieving parity in foreign policy institutions. (UNDP, 2015)

According to UN data, and in particular the Women in Diplomacy Index, women held around 20% of ambassadorial posts worldwide in 2024-2025, confirming their continued underrepresentation in ambassadorial positions across the globe. Although this figure has risen from 0.9% in 1968, women remain significantly underrepresented in the highest diplomatic offices. In 2024, women accounted for 21% of permanent representatives to the United Nations. Between 1992 and 2019, they made up only 13% of negotiators, 6% of mediators, and 6% of participants in peace processes worldwide.

Regional factors play a major role in shaping women's representation. In the Nordic countries, for example, women account for as much as 41% of ambassadors, whereas in the Middle East the figure is around 12%, and in Central Asia women ambassadors make up less than 5% of the total number of male heads of mission. Countries such as the Philippines (46%), Latvia (43%), and the Netherlands and Norway (42%) are among those with the highest shares of women ambassadors. Although women's advancement in diplomacy remains slow, there is a positive trend toward broader female participation in international relations. (UN, 2025)

In the countries of Central Asia, despite some positive developments, such as in Kazakhstan, where women career diplomats make up as much as 30%, women's participation in political life remains limited. This is especially evident in Kyrgyzstan, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, and Turkmenistan. Deep-rooted patriarchal norms, regional political culture, and institutional features continue to constrain the full realization of women's potential in national and international politics and diplomacy. Women remain significantly underrepresented in leadership positions, especially in foreign policy, security, and economics. Research shows that approximately 68-78% of top positions in diplomatic institutions worldwide are held by men, despite the stronger presence of women among regular staff. In Central Asia, the share of men in leadership roles reaches 90%. This gender gap is driven by professional barriers, limited opportunities, and slower career advancement. The main reasons include cultural norms, family responsibilities, and the persistence of discrimination against women, all of which continue to hinder women's progress in diplomacy and other professions.

In recent decades, Central Asia has faced the need to reform its political systems, including in relation to gender issues. In the context of growing international competition, geopolitical pressure, and increasing demands for inclusion, the representation of women in diplomacy has acquired strategic importance. International experience shows that women's participation in diplomacy broadens the traditional boundaries of the field, introduces new approaches, and opens up unconventional paths to problem-solving. Women diplomats possess important soft power potential, can act as mediators in conflicts, and are fully capable of representing state interests on the international stage as effectively as their male colleagues. Women are often more inclined toward compromise, which helps create an atmosphere of trust among negotiating partners and fosters a constructive approach to problem-solving. Entrusting women with senior representative roles in diplomacy also sends an important domestic and international signal that the state is committed to stable and harmonious development, both now and in the future. In today's world, where women have gained significant rights and opportunities, and where women presidents, ministers, and leaders are no longer exceptions, the presence of a substantial number of women in senior diplomatic and political positions is an essential sign of a developed society, one in which the rights and opportunities for professional self-realization are guaranteed to all citizens regardless of gender. Diversity is both important and necessary in diplomacy because it brings a broader perspective and greater sensitivity and respect toward different points of view. Policies that encourage women's participation in leadership positions are essential, because the more women hold strategic and decision-making roles, the greater their representation in the field will become.

This project aims to analyze how historical, cultural, and institutional factors have shaped the emergence of a female diplomatic voice in the countries of Central Asia, and to assess the current state of women's participation in the region's diplomatic and political institutions.

Literature Review and Methods

The study of women's participation in diplomacy at both the global and regional levels spans a wide range of disciplines, from political science and international relations to gender studies. The lack of empirical research focused specifically on the political sphere underscores the relevance of this study. A problem-oriented approach to data analysis made it possible to present relevant information flexibly from sources that differed in structure and content, and to produce an effective analysis of the main characteristics of women diplomats.

This study employed a broad methodological framework combining qualitative and quantitative approaches, including comparative analysis, content analysis, and case study methods. The comparative method was used to examine differences and similarities in approaches to women's participation in the diplomatic service in the five Central Asian countries: Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, and Turkmenistan. The empirical base included official reports and legal documents, including national gender equality strategies; academic articles, reviews, and reports by international organizations such as the UN, UNESCO, the OSCE, UN Women, and the ADB; and a documentary literature review of Central Asian and foreign authors based on legal analysis, national and international statistics, reports, scholarly studies, interviews, and public speeches. Content analysis made it possible to identify the rhetoric and discursive practices associated with women diplomats in official documents, speeches, government publications, and media materials.

The study draws conclusions about the distinctive features of women diplomats in Central Asian states on the basis of trends in their numbers, professional education, and performance in senior diplomatic positions, as well as case studies of Central Asian women participating in international platforms such as the UN, UNESCO, and others.

The analysis confirms the persistence of gender inequality in the diplomatic environment across the region, with particularly visible differences in low- and middle-income countries. Gender inequality, which cuts across all social classes and economic sectors, is reflected in the fact that most senior positions are still held by men. According to UNESCO, this inequality hinders progress toward Sustainable Development Goals 4 and 5, namely quality education and gender equality. The development and implementation of national action plans for UN Security Council Resolution 1325 of October 31, 2000, the first international document to formally recognize the key role of women in conflict prevention, peacebuilding, and post-conflict recovery, contributed to efforts to ensure women's equal participation in all mechanisms of conflict prevention and dispute resolution. The resolution became the foundation of the Women, Peace and Security agenda, under which further resolutions, including 1820, 1888, and 1960, were adopted on women's representation and participation. (UN, 2025)

From the perspective of the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development, women's participation in diplomacy is not only a gender issue but also an economic one: "Leaving women behind means not only ignoring the important contribution women make to the economy, but also wasting years of investment in the education of girls and young women" (OECD, 2019).

A review of international scholarship demonstrates the continuation of a long-standing pattern of male overrepresentation in diplomacy, alongside the persistence of formal restrictions and exclusionary practices affecting women. Existing studies focus mainly on Europe and North America and confirm that the highest diplomatic posts are still dominated by men. Kreft (2022) shows that women hold only 15% of ambassadorial posts worldwide, even though these are the highest positions for career diplomats and among the most prestigious political appointments. If one looks specifically at leadership positions in negotiations, the number of women is even lower. According to UN Women, in 2022 women accounted for only 9% of all negotiators, 2.5% of chief mediators, and 4% of signatories. In other words, core negotiating activity remains overwhelmingly male, while women are more often involved as observers, public advisers, or in purely administrative and support roles.

Among the key theoretical contributions are the works of Aggestam and Towns (2019) and Acha (2015), which emphasize the productive interaction between different strands of diplomacy and argue that including women in foreign policy decision-making contributes to more inclusive and sustainable international engagement. Particular attention has been paid to institutional barriers and gender quotas, as shown in the work of R. Feldman (2023), B. Kumari (2025), and publications by UN Women and the OSCE. Studies by the ADB (2020), UNDP (2022), and Central Asia Barometer (2023) provide important statistical data on women's political representation and public perceptions of their participation in governance and diplomacy, while also highlighting marked regional differences. Women's presence in

diplomacy brings mutual benefits, both for their own advancement and for broader global progress and transformation. (UNESCO, 2018)

Similar patterns of male overrepresentation can also be observed in international organizations, reflecting the gendered structure of diplomacy more broadly. In the European Council, for instance, women are systematically underrepresented in negotiating committees. Few women have been appointed to higher-level committees or to foreign policy portfolios. Unsurprisingly, the share of women at the highest ministerial level is the lowest among all EU institutions. At the same time, there are examples of stronger female representation in some international institutions, which may suggest that male dominance is less deeply entrenched there. For example, women make up 60% of Japanese delegations to the UN, even though they represent only 3% of Japanese ambassadors and 17% of diplomats overall. In the European Council, a similar tendency can be seen among newer member states, which generally appoint more women as Council negotiators than are represented in their national parliaments (Naurin and Naurin, 2019).

Recent UN and UNESCO reports note a shift in the gender composition of the diplomatic workforce. Increasing numbers of women are gaining qualifications and entering diplomatic service, a field that for a long time remained largely the preserve of men. According to UNESCO, the foreign ministries of Sweden and the United States have now reached gender parity, with women making up roughly 40-60% of staff, and the share of women in many other countries is rising rapidly (Aggestam and Towns, 2018).

In the post-Soviet context, important contributions include the studies of gender transformation and political culture by O. Porshneva (2023) and A. Pobedonostseva-Kaya (2024), which examine the consequences of the Soviet legacy and patriarchal norms in Central Asia. There is less research from a specifically regional perspective. Authors such as D. Tokhtakhodjaeva (1995) and K. N. Karabaeva (2023) shed light on the historical role of women in Central Asia, including their participation in socio-political processes.

In the Central Asian republics, women diplomats have made a meaningful contribution to the political processes of Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Uzbekistan during the independence period. However, despite these achievements, Central Asian women continue to face challenges similar to those encountered by their counterparts elsewhere in the world, including gender stereotypes, cultural expectations, and a long history of exclusion.

Results

A comparative analysis of women diplomats' representation in the countries of Central Asia over 30 years of independent development shows that women's entry into the foreign policy sphere was neither simple nor linear, and was initially shaped by the Soviet period. The data are based on open sources, official statements by foreign ministries, and publications by international organizations. This material made it possible to assess the degree to which women have been involved in shaping political directions in the region.

During the Soviet era, women from Central Asian countries were actively involved in administrative and foreign policy work, but within a strictly limited range of responsibilities. After the countries of the region gained independence in the 1990s, the number of women in senior foreign policy positions declined sharply as societies returned to more patriarchal structures. More broadly, Asia, including Central Asia, records the lowest share of women ambassadors, around 13% in 2025, which contrasts with higher figures in Europe and the Americas. At present, in 2025, women hold no more than 5% of leadership positions in diplomatic institutions across Central Asia. The highest level of representation is found in Kazakhstan, where reforms aimed at increasing gender inclusiveness have been introduced.

In Kazakhstan, although women held 56% of all civil service positions at the beginning of 2026, their share among political appointees was much lower, at only around 38.9% of leadership roles. Across

the independence period as a whole, women career diplomats accounted on average for 25-30%, with an even smaller share at senior levels. According to the Bureau of National Statistics of the Agency for Strategic Planning and Reforms of the Republic of Kazakhstan, the proportion of women ambassadors has fluctuated over the past 20 years but has never exceeded 5%. In 2005, there were no women among 36 ambassadors. In 2010, there were 2 women out of 44 ambassadors, or 4%. In 2015, there was 1 woman out of 57 ambassadors, or 1.7%. In 2022, there were 2 women out of 64 ambassadors, or 3%. In 2023, there were 4 women out of 68 ambassadors, or 5.8%. In 2024, there were 3 women out of 75 ambassadors, or 4%. In 2025, there was 1 woman out of 75 ambassadors, or 1%. At the beginning of 2026, women ambassadors accounted for less than 2%, with only 1 woman among 75 ambassadors extraordinary and plenipotentiary across 99 foreign missions. (Agency for Strategic Planning and Reforms of the Republic of Kazakhstan, 2025)

Table 1. Ratio of women ambassadors to the total number of ambassadors of the Republic of Kazakhstan

Category	2005 год	2010 год	2015 год	2022 год	2023 год	2024 год	2025 год
Men ambassadors	36	44	57	64	68	75	75
Women ambassadors	0	2	1	2	4	3	1
Percentage ratio	0	4	1,7	3	4	4	1

Source: Bureau of National Statistics of the Agency for Strategic Planning and Reforms of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

As of 2022, women in Uzbekistan held 27% of leadership positions across various sectors, including state institutions. Women made up 32% of the Legislative Chamber, the lower house of parliament, and 24.7% of the Senate, the upper house. In political parties, women accounted for 44%. Although there is no precise figure specifically for women diplomats in the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, their representation has been steadily growing within the framework of state gender policy. The government has actively promoted greater female participation in leadership positions, including in the diplomatic service, through reforms and equality policies. Overall, the role of women in Uzbekistan's socio-political life has strengthened significantly in recent years. (National Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan for Statistics, 2025).

In Kyrgyzstan, as of 2025-2026, women's participation in public administration has been increasing. By 2025, women held 33% of seats in the Jogorku Kenesh, while at the local level their share was around 40%. However, the exact proportion of women diplomats remains relatively low compared with men. Despite women's strong presence in some sectors, such as education, where they account for 86%, the diplomatic service remains marked by a gender gap, and women are less likely to hold senior positions. At the same time, the country has been actively expanding its international engagement by opening new embassies. Kyrgyzstan has taken steps to support women in diplomacy, including through regional training programs for young professionals. As in many countries of the region, the role of women diplomats in Kyrgyzstan is gradually growing, but men continue to dominate the upper levels of diplomatic power. (National Statistical Committee of the Kyrgyz Republic, 2025).

In Tajikistan, the number of women ambassadors in 2026 is not disclosed in open sources, but women are reported to hold 19% of leadership positions in the civil service, including in the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, and their numbers continue to grow. Women serve in important diplomatic roles, including as ambassadors to foreign countries and representatives in international missions. The number

of women in leadership positions, including in the diplomatic corps, is rising. In the first six months of 2025 alone, the number of women leaders increased by 13. By mid-2025, women held more than 1,100 leadership positions in state bodies. The share of women in parliament rose from 3% in 1995 to 24% in 2020. Tajikistan has pursued policies aimed at increasing women's representation in governance, which has also contributed to strengthening their role in diplomacy. (Agency for Statistics under the President of the Republic of Tajikistan, 2025)

In Turkmenistan, the number of women ambassadors in open sources for 2026 is not recorded, but women are reported to play an active role in the country's diplomacy. Women diplomats are described as important contributors, and the number of those seeking careers in this field is growing, including in missions to the United Nations. (State Committee of Turkmenistan on Statistics, (2025)

Table 2. Women's representation in diplomacy

Country	Share of women career diplomats in the MFA system, % (2025)	Women ambassadors (2025), number	Gender strategy in place
Kazakhstan	30	1	Yes, since 2021
Kyrgyzstan	30	0	Yes
Uzbekistan	23	0	Yes
Tajikistan	18	0	No
Turkmenistan	No data	0	No

Source: UN Women Central Asia Report 2025, OSCE Gender Equality Review 2025, ADB Gender Strategy Report 2025.

Taken together, these data show that throughout the independence period all Central Asian republics have made only limited progress toward gender equality in diplomacy, with the clearest gains visible in Kazakhstan, and to a lesser extent in Kyrgyzstan and Uzbekistan. A number of supportive measures have helped increase the number of women diplomats, and Kazakhstan and Kyrgyzstan have made some progress in the broader civil service. In Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, and Turkmenistan, women's participation in diplomacy remains low. The table clearly demonstrates the need for a more unified regional approach to promoting gender equality in diplomacy, stronger institutional support, and comprehensive strategies to involve women in international processes.

The analysis also shows that on international platforms, women from Central Asia tend to be represented mainly in humanitarian, cultural, and educational issues. At the same time, their participation is growing in projects related to sustainable development, water diplomacy, and climate change. Despite growing attention to gender equality, women's participation in diplomatic service across Central Asia remains relatively low, and progress toward restoring gender balance in diplomacy continues to be slow and uneven.

Discussion

During the independence period, the sphere of foreign policy and diplomacy in the Central Asian republics went through difficult times. The strong political and economic potential inherited from the Soviet period, including major international schools and institutions in various fields, steadily weakened from the 1990s onward and encountered serious problems. This was followed by years of sharp and sustained decline across all areas of international activity, including reduced or nonexistent funding for international research and a lack of demand for both its results and the work of foreign policy professionals more broadly. Many research institutes involved in international studies were closed, while

those that continued to function often lacked the material and technical resources needed for effective work. All of this led to a general decline in productivity in foreign policy studies and diplomacy.

The findings point to real progress in the inclusion of women in diplomatic service in Central Asia, but that progress remains uneven and is accompanied by a range of persistent problems. The main barrier is gender stereotypes, which remain deeply rooted in both public consciousness and institutional practice. Traditional gender roles continue to hinder women's career advancement. Despite the existence of international commitments and national programs, such as gender equality strategies in Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Uzbekistan, women's participation in diplomacy remains limited both quantitatively and qualitatively. It should also be noted that across the region women face additional obstacles, including restricted professional mobility, low representation in the leadership of academic institutions, and insufficient support in human resources policy formation. Unequal access to educational opportunities and overseas internships further reduces women's chances of entering global political and diplomatic processes.

Research by international scientists points to multiple causes of gender inequality in diplomacy, although the degree of women's underrepresentation varies by country, region, field of expertise, age, and culture (Avolio et al., 2020). According to the UNESCO Report (2024), women's participation in diplomacy worldwide ranges from 8% to 63%, with an average of 30%. The report also highlights the conflict many women face between professional ambition and family responsibilities. Studies further show that low female representation in diplomacy is driven by discrimination, including gender, racial, and class-based discrimination, as well as sociocultural factors, institutional patterns of bias, and cultural norms embedded in social structures. As a result, only a minority of women, on average 25%, advance toward leadership, and just 5% reach senior positions (Gupta, 2020). Factors such as cultural expectations and family responsibilities, including the double burden of paid work and domestic duties, continue to impede women's advancement across many professions. When combined, these forces can perpetuate a hostile environment for women and lead to their exclusion from the diplomatic community (Saunders, 2020).

A comparative analysis of the region shows that more open political systems and states oriented toward integration with international institutions, such as Kazakhstan, Uzbekistan, and Kyrgyzstan, provide more opportunities for the career advancement of women diplomats. This is reflected in appointments as permanent representatives to the UN and in participation in international conferences, forums, and intergovernmental negotiations. By contrast, in Turkmenistan and Tajikistan women's participation in diplomacy is more often confined to support or administrative roles, which is linked to the closed nature of their political systems and weaker institutional support for gender initiatives.

Gender equality in Kazakhstan has been actively promoted through legislative reforms, the ratification of international conventions such as CEDAW, and the introduction of quotas aimed at increasing women's role in governance, the economy, and anti-violence efforts. The country has adopted the Law on State Guarantees of Equal Rights and Equal Opportunities for Men and Women (2009) and the Family and Gender Policy Concept to 2030. A 30% quota for women and youth in party lists has increased women's representation in parliament, up to 27%, as well as in local bodies. Women make up a significant share of the workforce, including up to 39% of leadership posts in the civil service. However, despite women's very high level of education, with an index of 0.999, gaps remain in pay and political representation. In April 2024, a law was adopted that strengthened liability for domestic violence, including the criminalization of battery. According to the Global Gender Gap Report 2025, Kazakhstan ranks 92nd out of 148 countries. Current efforts focus mainly on women's economic empowerment, childcare infrastructure, and combating domestic violence.

In recent years, Uzbekistan has moved along a path of reforms aimed at promoting gender equality and expanding women's rights and opportunities across all sectors of society. Building on progressive legislative changes and a renewed national commitment, the country amended its Constitution to reaffirm

equal rights and opportunities for women and men in public and state affairs, adopted the Law on Guarantees of Equal Rights and Opportunities for Women and Men in 2019, and launched the National Gender Strategy for 2021-2030. These achievements reflect Uzbekistan's intention to secure equal representation of women in politics, leadership, and decision-making, paving the way for a more inclusive and equitable future. At the same time, despite these efforts, women continue to face structural barriers and remain widely underrepresented, especially in the executive, judicial, and state sectors. Overcoming these obstacles and accelerating progress will require systemic change, institutional commitment, and collective action.

In Kyrgyzstan, gender equality is guaranteed in law by the Constitution, which provides for equal rights, but in practice serious problems linked to patriarchal norms and discrimination remain. Measures to increase women's participation in politics, up to 33% in parliament by 2025, and in the economy are being actively implemented, and a National Strategy to 2030 is in place. The strategy focuses on women's economic empowerment, protection from discrimination, support for rural women, and the development of women's entrepreneurship. Laws have been adopted on state guarantees of equal rights and on social and legal protection from domestic violence, while liability for domestic violence and bride kidnapping has been strengthened. At the same time, the country faces serious problems that hinder broader progress for women, including poverty, unemployment, and declining access to education, especially among women in rural areas. Income inequality between men and women persists, and many women remain concentrated in the informal sector. Rising unemployment and poverty under market conditions have worsened women's social situation. Moreover, traditional norms in Kyrgyz society have historically defined teaching and medicine as women's work, while engineering has remained a male domain. The sectors most accessible to women do not provide adequate pay or guarantee status in society. Opportunities that could arise from socioeconomic and cultural change, including advances in medicine and healthcare, have not been fully realized. Poverty and the collapse of the previous social protection system have contributed to worsening conditions for women amid the broader decline in living standards (Karabaeva, 2023).

At the same time, it is important to highlight positive examples of women ambassadors and women politicians whose public roles and active foreign policy engagement provide role models for young women in the region. Such figures contribute not only to women's advancement in diplomacy but also to the transformation of public opinion about women's capacity to participate in foreign policy decision-making. The discussion therefore points to the need for a comprehensive approach to achieving gender balance in diplomacy. This approach must include not only institutional reform, but also transformation in the educational, media, and political environment. Women must have continuous access to education and professional development at different levels in order to take part fully in public life. Taking these facts into account, and recognizing the value of diplomacy, the republics of Central Asia should strive for equality of opportunity and for broader inclusion of different social groups in diplomacy. Only under these conditions will sustainable and equal participation of women in the diplomatic processes of Central Asia become possible.

Today, despite all the efforts women are making to integrate into the diplomatic community, those efforts remain insufficient so long as underrepresentation continues to define the professional landscape. As UNESCO IESALC Director Francesc Pedró noted, "Young people must be educated in institutions where gender equality is promoted and welcomed; universities should lead by example" (UNESCO, 2020).

Efforts to increase diversity in leadership positions within diplomatic and political institutions are essential to reducing the unfriendly working environment often faced by young diplomats. Women should also be encouraged to take on leadership roles through policies that support their participation, because the competence is clearly there, and the more women occupy strategic and senior positions, the stronger their representation in the field will be, along with broader debate and more active struggle for

equal opportunities (Howe-Walsh and Turnbull, 2016). Strategies designed to help diplomats balance family responsibilities, such as childcare support and maternity leave for researchers, also help prevent women from leaving the diplomatic environment (Barres, 2006).

A number of steps can be taken to improve gender equality in diplomacy, beginning with basic education. Culture and family traditions often discourage girls from pursuing diplomatic careers from an early age. Primary and secondary schools can help overcome this pattern by presenting a wider range of career possibilities and highlighting examples of successful women diplomats.

Governments should promote initiatives that encourage girls, even while still in secondary school, to consider political and diplomatic careers. Universities should develop joint projects with schools aimed at encouraging women to choose careers in diplomacy. In this sense, the discussion once again points to the need for a comprehensive approach to achieving gender balance in diplomacy. It must include not only institutional reforms but also changes in the educational, media, and political environment. Only then will sustainable and equal participation of women in the political processes of Central Asia become possible.

Conclusion

This study makes it possible to draw several important conclusions about the role of women in the political sphere of the Central Asian countries. Historical analysis shows that women's participation in shaping the region's intellectual and political processes was sporadic for much of the past, and that more active involvement began only toward the end of the twentieth century. Despite the positive changes achieved in recent decades, women's participation in diplomacy remains limited and uneven across the countries of the region. Women are still underrepresented in leadership positions, and as of 2024-2025 they accounted for no more than 2-5% of ambassadors in Central Asia. Despite progress, diplomatic space continues to be shaped largely by male norms, with persistent problems such as sexism, work-life balance pressures, and constraints related to the so-called trailing spouse issue.

The most favorable situation can be observed in Kazakhstan and Uzbekistan, where measures have been introduced to strengthen gender equality institutionally, including in the broader political and academic environment. Kyrgyzstan also demonstrates a relatively open political system that allows women to participate in international political and academic activity. Research shows that when women hold diplomatic posts, they often give greater priority to social cohesion, environmental sustainability, and in some cases more effective conflict resolution. At the same time, Tajikistan and Turkmenistan continue to face structural limitations linked to political closure, the lack of programs for women's advancement, and weak civil society engagement.

The main challenges therefore include:

- gender stereotypes within the professional diplomatic environment
- limited mobility and career prospects for women
- an insufficient number of women in senior academic and diplomatic posts
- weak integration of women into international political and institutional processes

Recommendations

1. Develop national strategies to promote women in politics and diplomacy. Gender indicators should be incorporated into the personnel policies of foreign ministries, and equal conditions should be ensured in the recruitment, training, and promotion of diplomatic personnel.

2. Expand educational and career opportunities. Policies should support women's education in STEM fields and create more opportunities for international internships in order to broaden the outlook and experience of young diplomats. Specialized training programs, scholarships, internships, and exchanges with leading schools around the world should also be developed for women diplomats.

3. Increase public recognition. Women leaders in diplomacy and politics should receive greater support in the media, positive role models should be promoted, and public demand for gender balance should be strengthened.

4. Promote regional cooperation. Platforms should be created for exchanging experience among Central Asian countries in advancing women in diplomacy and politics, including forums, round tables, and joint programs.

5. Strengthen monitoring and reporting. Indicators and evaluation mechanisms should be developed to track progress in women's participation in diplomacy, with regular reporting at both the national and regional levels.

6. Integrate gender analysis into the development of international strategies. Women experts should be involved in shaping foreign policy agendas, including peacebuilding missions, environmental diplomacy, human rights, and sustainable development. Implementing these recommendations would help create a more just, inclusive, and sustainable environment in Central Asia and would represent an important step toward achieving gender equality in diplomacy.

7. Create more diverse panels and expand women's participation in expert discussions and political debate. Tools should be developed and promoted to strengthen gender equality in research and governance.

8. Introduce formalized and transparent recruitment and promotion procedures. This would help reduce bias and make diplomatic institutions more inclusive.

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